

A Critical Exploration of the Challenges
Faced by Social Workers when
Identifying At-Risk Children.

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Abstract

This study examines the challenges faced by social workers in the process of identifying at-risk children. While social workers are essential in protecting the most vulnerable children, they face different challenges. This research highlights the systematic, organisational, structural, and personal hurdles that affect the effectiveness of this identification process. This research will investigate and examine significant challenges in the assessment process by analysing serious case studies as secondary analysis. This study emphasises the need for enhanced training, resources, and strategies to improve outcomes. Emphasising recurring primary discussions and the necessity for enhanced policy.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

“Children are highly vulnerable. They have little or no power to protect or provide for themselves, and little influence on so much is vital to their well-being. Children need others to speak for them, as they need decision makers who put their well-being ahead of selfish adult interests.” (Oaks, 2012, p.1)

1.1 Introduction

In the United Kingdom, in the year ending 2024, on average, at least one child is killed a week, with the most vulnerable group to most likely experience harm, death, or neglect being children under the age of one (NSPCC, 2024). The majority of child homicides likely are perpetrated by their parents or step-parents (NSPCC, 2024; WHO, 2024). In addition, child deaths between the years 2014 and 2017 were as much as 44% maltreatment deaths (Brandon et al., 2020). The World Health Organisation (2024) describes child maltreatment as abuse or neglect that occurs to children under age 18. WHO (2024) highlights various types of child maltreatment, such as physical, emotional, sexual, and negligent, which impact child development, dignity, and health. Child maltreatment can cause death or significant consequences on mental and physical enhancement and can cause post-traumatic stress disorder and depression in childhood or adulthood (Bailhache et al., 2013). Despite this, only a fraction of child victims of maltreatment ever get support from health professionals (WHO, 2024). Consequently, this highlights a global issue that needs attention and improved intervention strategies. Nonetheless, social workers perform a key function in society by addressing the needs of children (Thompson, 2024). People often view social workers negatively due to their experiences or media coverage (Thompson, 2024). Despite this, social workers are the people ‘in the middle’ whose duties and responsibilities lie within the care and protection of the most vulnerable (Thompson, 2024). This research aims to explore challenges associated with the identification process. It is crucial to highlight that the first initial assessment carried out by a social worker is one of the most important gatherings and evidencing of information about child welfare, environment, and social needs (Milner et al., 2020). Social workers need to gather unbiased information about children despite information provided to them by their parents (Webb, 2019). Parents' information must be treated critically, as it may be influenced by a desire to conceal abuse or neglect. This research aims to explore some of these challenges and difficulties that social workers experience in their assessments.

Firstly, this research will examine burnouts experienced by social workers. Although burnout refers to the physical and mental state of the individuals (HSE, 2024), it affects the decision-making and social workers' judgment (Marc and Osvat, 2013; Abuaddous et al., 2018). Literature highlights the correlation between burnout and the inability to make correct judgments. Marc and Osvat's (2013) study explores the effects of burnout leading to physical and emotional exhaustion. Further issues will revolve around the multi-structured organisation of social settings. Multi-structured settings refer to governmental and local bodies in processes and information sharing (Fish, 2015). Multi-structured settings refer to information sharing between agencies, such as health professionals, police, education settings, and child protection services (Mitchell and Demir, 2021). Although multi-structured settings aim to collaboratively share important information within the organization, provide thorough support, and implement interventions for families, they often fail to achieve these goals (Fish, 2015). It's crucial to highlight that failings within communication lead to inaccurate information and create failings in the initial stages of the assessment (Jacklin et al., 2006). Social workers who lack a comprehensive understanding of the issues make wrong judgements or often do not acknowledge the extent of the problems, creating further barriers to correctly identifying children at risk (Jacklin et al., 2006). This research will explore cultural and religious assumptions as a contributive factor in the decision-making process (Dalley, 2019). Arguably ideology and cultural assumptions impact decision-making in social settings (Hendricks et al., 2020). Differences between culture and religion may create a barrier within understanding and support settings (NSPP, 2014). Leading often to the isolation of the most vulnerable children (NSPSS, 2014). Assessment tools are adapted to ensure cultural and religious sensitivity and to explore the person's culture and impact on their life (NSPCC, 2014). Finally, by exploring assessments carried out of children in special circumstances, for example, in substance abuse homes. Understanding family dynamics and early intervention is crucial to correctly identifying vulnerabilities within family dynamics (Baldwin, 2021).

Although primary research provides practical insights that enrich social workers' perspectives (Alston, 2020), the reluctance of some social workers to participate in research initiatives (Power and Dean, 2023) deemed the search for primary research in this context unfeasible. Despite the authors' engagement with local councils and reaching out for participation, the researcher concentrated on exploring this project by relying on governmental and official sources and reviewing three serious case studies of Victoria Climbié, Peter Connelly, and Arthur Lavinjo-Hughes. Moreover, researching topics involving children is a sensitive subject to analyse (Powell et al., 2018). Despite critically important input from children as a collective method to understand issues and concerns, researchers often abandon their projects or modify them, resulting in children's voices not being heard (Powel et al., 2018). The

utilisation of secondary sources presents concerns regarding the research design and methodologies employed, in addition to the researcher's subjectivities and biases (Brayman, 2016). Nonetheless, by applying credible sources that have undergone extensive research standards, the author attempted to minimise the possibility of incorporating potentially erroneous material or highlighting the weakness of the chosen sources. Furthermore, this desk-project research did not have ethical difficulties while including children as a key expository subject. Furthermore, the author complied with the London Metropolitan (2022) guidelines for professional conduct.

This research aims to explore and analyse key issues within the assessment process by reviewing serious case studies. As indicated, many challenges and recommendations within cases often refer back to the initial stages of the assessment. With indication and question, what went wrong, and where has the communication broken down to prevent the outcome? This research author aims to address and explore key connections between social workers and the outcomes of this process. This area of study is crucial yet frequently receives insufficient attention and examination.

1.2 Understanding the multifaced role of the social worker

The widespread perception of social workers is that they portray a 'caring' and 'helping' profession (Thompson, 2024). Despite the very demanding nature of the job and media criticism, social workers play a crucial role within society (Thompson, 2024). Thompson (2024) argues that although social workers often aim to achieve a positive outcome, what is achievable due to challenges and the constitutional settings in which they operate can vary (Asquith et al., 2005). Thompson (2024) argues that social work is focused on resolving social issues, fostering social change, and improving the welfare of individuals and communities. Compared with Hope and Van Wyk (2018), who argue that social workers typically undergo minimal training and frequently depend on social stereotypes and cultural assumptions, adopting intrusive practices. According to the latest statistics, around 1 in every 30 children were classified as in need (Department for Education, 2024). The term 'children in need' refers to those who require assistance and protection due to potential risks to their health or development (Department for Education, 2024). Historically, social work has its roots in the social reform movements of the late 1960s and early 1970s, where growing awareness of poverty, inequalities, and social injustices arose through the surface (Jones, 2019). The historical changes are essential for understanding the shift from charitable endeavours in the late 1960s into a recognised profession that combines sociology, psychology, and public policy (Jones, 2020). The introduction of the Children Act (1989) provided a beginning and solid grounds that no child should suffer any harm, neglect, or abuse. As highlighted in the Children Act (1989), it supports children who experience difficulties in their families and protects them from maltreatment. Furthermore, to the foundational principles established by the Children Act (1989), social workers continue to evolve in their approach and advocacy within social support. Social workers engage in various environmental settings, such as schools, hospitals, community centres, and governmental agencies (Jones, 2019). However, this research will concentrate on social workers within family settings. Next, the introduction of the Children and Social Work Act (2017) has highlighted the role of social workers, which includes supporting individuals and their families through difficult times and ensuring that vulnerable people, including children and adults, are safeguarded from harm and abuse; improved collaboration with other agencies to improve responses, and support needed. Their work focuses on individuals with experiences of abuse, mental health issues, or substance abuse (the College of Social Workers, 2014). According to Social Work England (2017), as much as 80% of social workers were satisfied with their training, understanding of applying law, and engaging with children and vulnerable adults. However, social workers, as little as 24% felt not respected within their profession (The College of Social Workers, 2014). Hanley (2024) highlights negative public perception, mostly through consistent media attention, as one of the key factors

contributing towards underappreciation within their profession. Social workers face constant challenges within society to 'improve' the quality of care of children and their families (Hanley, 2024).

1.3 Role, powers and responsibilities

Social workers perform a multi-layered job role. Thompson (2024) argues that their job structure is based on the continuous between care and control. The line between care and control can be problematic, as social workers have dual responsibilities: to provide and care for their community. Social work control can be seen as care (Thompson, 2024). However, recognising that control can often lead to conflicts and tensions between social workers and clients. For example, in such cases where additional care is needed with someone who suffers from mental health problems, a social worker's attention drifted towards 'policing' at the expense of meeting basic needs (Thompson, 2024). Failure to address those issues can lead to an even more stressful situation. Consequently, the balance between care and control is a difficult one to maintain and, therefore, an important one to navigate (Thompson, 2024). The most recent attempt to specify the roles of social workers has been by Social Work England (2020), which highlighted that social workers will embrace and promote the fundamental rights of all people. Social workers will respect the dignity and worth of everyone and support people to be in control of their lives (Social Work England, 2020). Moreover, by continually working and being alert to any potential harm or neglect, they are a collaborative person who works closely with other professionals. This is one of many duties highlighted in Social Work England (2020).

Although social workers possess various powers, they often show hesitation in their usage (Okitipki, 2011). Practitioners perceive their function as facilitating children's attachment within their social and family settings (Okitipki, 2011). Removal of children into care is not seen as a favourable option due to the potential for poor outcomes (Okitipki, 2011). Removal is seen as a final measure after the failure of all efforts to sustain or restore effective parenting (Okitipki, 2011). Dominelli (2002) identified three distinct approaches used by social workers: therapeutic, transformational view, and social order approaches. The therapeutic approach evolves around seeking the best possible well-being outcome for individuals, groups or their communities (Dominelli, 2002). For example, this involves not only providing support and guidance but also helping clients develop the skills and resources they need to navigate their challenges effectively (Okitipki, 2011). The transformational view is seen as a development of 'mutual' cooperation and sport within society so that most disadvantaged people can gain power over their own lives (Cree and Myers, 2008). Meanwhile, social order views contemplate the structural aspects of social work by assessing how institutional factors interact with personal challenges (Cree and Myers, 2008). However, despite all the different approaches and perspectives,

the main outcome and responsibilities of practitioners remain the same: to care for and support (Oktipki, 2011).

1.4 Risk Assessments and interventions

Social workers undertake significant efforts to identify at-risk adolescents. Social workers face crucial decisions; with information based on them, they assess whether a child's removal from home is the best intervention (Osimo and Benbenishty, 2004). Social workers judge structural risk assessments, which navigate and support their decisions (Osimo and Benbenishty, 2004). However, gathering information, shifting it carefully, and coming to an 'objective' and 'accurate' decision can be problematic (Milner et al., 2020). The complexity of this task arises from each child's circumstances and environmental settings (Milner et al., 2020). As highlighted by Hood and Allison (2001), there is a general lack of understanding of risk assessments, which often concentrate on process rather than outcome. Titterton (2005, p. 83) describes assessments as a 'process of estimating and evaluating risk, understood as the possibility of beneficial and harmful outcomes.'. For Hepworth et al., (2002), assessment is analysing and synthesising new information as it emerges through the entire course of the given case. As hinted in Working Together to Safeguard Children guidance (2006), the purpose of the assessments is to gather information about child and family; thus, social work practises have moved away from approaches that emphasise the need to diagnose the problems of the individuals, towards a more empathic form of practice which focuses on the individuals within social settings. Working Together to Safeguard Children (2006) states that assessments should analyse their needs/ and or nature and level of any risk or harm; to analyse risk if children are likely to suffer harm or neglect.

It is crucial to emphasise that the initial stage of the evaluation involves collecting all external information to fully understand the child's situation (Webb, 2019). This information or these interviews can be from the parents, school, and any other professionals, as well as from the personal observation of the social worker (Webb, 2019). Helping a child begins at the very beginning of the assessment process (Milner et al., 2020). As pointed out by Webb (2019), assessment is a 'thinking process that seeks out the meaning of the case situation (p. 58). However, to lay out the initial assessment, it's important to understand why a problem exists in the first place (Webb, 2019). Webb (2019) classified assessment stages into three factors: individual factors, situational factors, and factors in the support system. Often, initial assessments lead social workers to identify needs for specialised medical, psychological, or educational evaluation and to make appropriate referrals for the child (Webb, 2019). Webb (2019) argues that assessments of children are always provisional since children's growth is ongoing; thus, assessments should be repeated periodically to allow for natural developmental

changes. The next stage of the assessment involves evaluating the 'problem' of the situation, in simple terms, what the current needs are for the child to meet 'basic' demands (Webb, 2019). The second stage of the evaluation system focuses on comprehending and assessing the problems' nature, psychological and environmental issues, the starting point and length of the prospective problem, and the perception of support (Webb, 2019). The final stage within the assessments evolves around factors in the support system friends, family, peers, neighbourhood and the outcome of the support given (Webb, 2019).

Chapter 2: Methodology

To explore social workers' challenges in the identification process, the author aims to explore these issues through secondary analysis of existing data to answer the research question, particularly by examining serious case studies. The author achieves secondary data analysis by reviewing available resources collected by governments, institutions, or various agencies for analytical purposes (Clark, 2014). Using secondary data offers an alternative to collecting primary data, which, in this context, was impossible despite the author's attempts to engage participants. By examining existing data, researchers can uncover patterns and insights that may not be readily apparent through primary data collection (Johnston, 2014); consequently, this method, will allow the author to conduct a broader analysis of the challenges of social workers in the identification process of children at risk.

Secondary analysis involves examining data originally collected by another party for a different primary purpose (Johnston, 2014). Utilising existing data presents an achievable solution for researchers with restricted time and resources (Johnston, 2014). Moreover, secondary data analysis is an empirical endeavour that follows the fundamental research principles applicable to studies employing primary data, involving a systematic approach like other research methodologies (Johnston, 2014). In this research, the author will analyse serious case studies. Serious case studies are local enquiries into the death or serious injury of a child where abuse or neglect is known or suspected (Brandon et al., 2009). Drawing attention to an analytical framework, the author aims to look beyond the details of the recommendation to understand the deeper level of issues that may have led to child death. This approach provides a shift from individual blaming and focusses on flaws inherent in our systems for safeguarding children, and therefore a context for learning and recommendation (Brandon et al., 2010). For example, in research conducted by Dickens et al. (2022), which analysed a series of case studies from 1998 to 2019. Dickens et al. (2022) produced an analysis that included a series of thematic briefings, which highlighted key messages from the reviews and emphasised practice recommendations. Analysis of 21 years of SCRs led to a broader understanding of underlying requirements, expectations and operation of new recommendations (Dickens et al., 2022). Analysis of Dickens et al., (2022) draw attention to the importance of reasonable workloads, sufficient and experienced staff, improved clear and courageous thinking of 'ask the next question', and enhance inter-agency working and communications. Secondary analysis facilitates profound examination, enables reconsideration of data, decreases overlap in research, and emphasises the consequences of insufficient search (Wickham, 2019).

The author of this research adapted secondary analysis for a comprehensive understanding of the challenges of social workers. This approach facilitates the exploration of new research questions, enhances the reproducibility of studies and maximises the value of previously gathered information. The accessibility of serious case studies can vary, depending on different factors such as the type of study, platforms used to publish these studies, and intended audience (Sidebotham, 2016). As argued by Heathon (1998), secondary analysis allows for unexpected topics that emerge from primary research to be further analysed, and these are worthy topics of investigation precisely because they have emerged spontaneously without being directly solicited by the researchers (Heathon, 1998). Despite this, all serious case studies used in this research were available through the governmental website and the NSPCC platform, which provided free and easily accessible files for analysis.

The first SCR used in this research is Victoria Climbié, conducted by Lord Laming. The Lord Laming enquiry aimed at analysing failings within social workers. Lord Laming (2004), recommendation led to the introduction of Every Child Matters Act in 2004. The second SCR used is Peter Connelly 'Baby P'. The first report was carried out by the Haringey Local Safeguarding Children Board in 2008, and the second report was carried out in 2009 by the Haringey LSCH board. Thirdly, Arthur Lavinjo-Hughes SCR was conducted by the Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel in 2022. All three SCRs enquiries were aimed at analysing whether all recommendations were achievable and measurable.

On the other hand, available data from secondary analysis are not collected to address the particular research question or to test a particular hypothesis (Cheng and Phillips, 2014). Similarly, the data may not be collected for research purposes; they aim to address different audiences and/or receivers of these reports (Cheng and Phillips, 2014). A further limitation of the analysis of existing data is that the researchers who are analysing the data are not usually the same individuals as those involved in the data collection process (Cheng and Phillips, 2014). Therefore, they are probably unaware of study-specific data collection processes that may be important to the interpretation of the findings (Cheng and Phillips, 2014).

Furthermore, the limitation of SCRS is the quality of SCRs. Firstly, this includes irrelevant details, failing to ask why, and neglecting to focus on the child or address their perspectives (Dickens et al., 2022). Moreover, recommendations are unclear as to which specific individuals or organisations they were referring to (Dickens et al., 2022). The Serious Case Review Panel (2014) argues that serious case studies often overlook human motivation and fail to emphasise children's experiences. In similar findings, the Wood Review (2016) highlighted that serious case studies frequently concentrate on blaming aspects rather than learning experiences. The Wood Review (2016) identifies further shortcomings in significant

case studies, including prolonged publication delays and recommendations that are often foreseeable or vague, failing to meet specific requirements or address particular organisations.

While SCR is a secondary analysis, there is objectivity for the reader to consider during this analysis. It's vital to address the emotional impact on the researcher and reader. Detailed information about events and severe descriptions of abuse and harm to the children create an emotional impact of powerlessness and frustration. This ethical dilemma or emotional sensibility can influence the decision or outcomes of the analysis (Pearlman, 2023). Pearlman (2023) argues that emotional sustainability sharpens attention to how researchers analyse and gather data. Pearlman (2023) emphasises the importance of acknowledging emotions; otherwise, we may overlook critical data or factors that could impact the results. Despite the limitations of secondary analysis and feelings of powerlessness, the author will maintain objectivity in the analysis, ensuring that this research's findings remain unbiased.

Chapter 3: Literature review

3.1 Social workers & burnout

According to the latest statistics for the year ending 2024, Child Protection and Social Welfare has 399,500 children classified as in need with more than 621,900 referrals received in 2024 (Children in Need, 2024). Yet, with increasingly large numbers and complex caseloads, social workers have the highest levels of stress and burnout of all human services professions (Ravalier et al., 2020; Burns and MacCarthy, 2012). The UK Health and Safety Executive (HSE, 2024) reported that 29.6 million days were lost due to work-related ill health in the year ending 2023/24, with most caused by stress, anxiety, or depression. This accounted for the highest score from human/health and social work, with as much as 6000 work-related to ill health per 100000 workers (HSE, 2024). Consequently, social work is recognised as one of the most stressful occupations in the United Kingdom, with very high levels of stress, anxiety, or depression (HSE, 2024). Knowing the causes of work-related stress, especially understanding contributing factors to 'burnout', with recognition of the problem, can be essential for both the individual as well as for their organisation (Marc and Osvat, 2013). The consequences of burnout, as argued by Marc and Osvat (2013) contribute towards work performances, employee health problems, lower productivity and potential conflicts within the organisation. Burnout within the workplace is referred to as a 'unique effective response to the prolonged and chronic interpersonal stressors which depletes a person's energetic and coping resources' (Naveed and Rana, 2013, p.114). For example, in the research conducted by Marc and Osvat (2013), who conducted interviews with 18 social workers, one of the main themes within social workers was excessive case overload, time constraints, unappreciation within social settings and lack of support from organisations and colleagues. Marc and Osvat (2013) highlighted within the study that burnout among social workers leads to emotional and physical exhaustion. It is crucial to highlight that according to psychology studies, burnout is responsible for the ability to make decisions in terms of memory tasks or judgement (Abuaddous et al., 2018). Abuaddous et al., (2018) argue that burnout employee as their coping mechanism is avoidance in sensitive decision-making. A similar study conducted by Michailidis and Banks (2016) supports the argument that if the job requires important decision-making, employees who are under burnout are found prone to risky decision-making. Research by McFadden (2015), supported by A Community Care, demonstrated that 91% of social workers experienced emotional exhaustion, while an additional 61% reported symptoms of depersonalisation. Depersonalisation impairs the integrated functions of consciousness, memory, identity, and perception, resulting in a reduced sense of self-worth and identity (Simeon, 2004). Depersonalisation is associated with significant stress and/or impairment,

which is adaptive behaviour by individuals who become overwhelmed with the circumstances they are dealing with, allowing for emotional detachment (Simeon, 2004). Depersonalisation is defined as a mental health disorder 'where you have the feeling of being outside yourself and observing your actions, feelings or thoughts from a distance, where you feel world is unreal' (National Health Service, 2023, p1). Consequently, social worker burnout can lead to poor evaluation or decision-making within their assessment and judgement (Marc and Osvat, 2013; Michailidis and Banks, 2016).

3.2 Multi-structure of the organisation

The next challenge faced by social workers is the multi-structure of the organisation. Information available to social workers, or the full range of the evidence, is difficult to obtain (Munro, 1999). Initial assessments within the referral fails to collect information from other professional bodies. For example, according to research conducted by Munro (1999), who evaluated 45 cases of mistakes made by social workers in their assessment framework, common theme emerged as cases had not been shared between agencies. Furthermore, twelve reports emphasised by Munro (1999) determined that if the information of specialists had been shared, the risk to the children could have been evaluated with greater accuracy. With a history of evidence, much of the history was overlooked, alongside the error of communication between agencies (Munro, 1999). In similar findings, Pinkney et al. (2018) define multi-agency working together, which should be close collaboration and information sharing between governmental bodies and local authorities. In research conducted by Pinkey et al., (2018), who analysed the views of 92 social workers across England and Wales, highlighted that information sharing is problematic within their profession. Data protection rights and confusion associated with what information can be shared and what information can be disclosed create further barriers among social workers (Piney et al., 2018). It's crucial to highlight that limited sources and information available to social workers can lead to poor decision-making. The inability to see the full extent of where and what the problem is (Jacklin et al., 2006). With a lack of data, social workers face further challenges in identifying accurately the needs of the children (Jacklin et al., 2006). Mitchell and Demir (2021), information sharing in social care is a key way of addressing risks, vulnerabilities, and uncertainties. For example, in the case of Daniel Pelka, age 4, who died due to head injury and malnutrition in 2013, Coventry Safeguarding Children Board highlighted in serious case reports that sharing information between agencies has failed with an additional lack of assessment carried out by social workers (Lock, 2013). Although the school has raised concerns about Daniel's weight and seeking food, social services due to the heavy caseloads, with high levels of a backlog of referrals and a lack of professional curiosity contributed to Daniel's death (Lock, 2013). Social workers shifted attention from Daniel to their parents as there were incidents of domestic violence in the family home (Lock, 2013). Moreover, the failings of

the police and referrals team, which, as described, had numerous occasions for additional assessment, were never followed up (Lock, 2013). For example, Daniel attended the hospital due to a minor head injury in March 2008 after the first initial visit to A&E health visitor received a letter stating about domestic abuse within the family home; however, the opportunity for intervention was not taken to explore further. The complexity of Daniel Pelka's death, who suffered 41 injuries at the time of his death, highlighted multi-agency failure, not only by social workers but also by health visitors, schools, and police (Lock, 2013).

3.3 Cultural and religious assumptions

Child and family social workers operate in client-facing job roles, where they make decisions about children and their families (Mitchell and Demir, 2022). Thus, social workers' values and beliefs, are shifted through different lenses from cultural dynamics or trends (Reamer, 2018). Social workers should challenge their own beliefs, and avoid any assumptions about other individuals (Reamer, 2018). For example, the research conducted by Dalley (1991) who conducted interviews with social workers, in three Scottish towns, discovered that ideology within social workers was a key factor in decision-making process. Cultural stereotypes and assumptions about other groups create barriers within social settings (Dalley, 1991). Dalley (1991) argues that assumption may have a significant impact on the organisational process because professional behaviour is influenced by the value of judgments made about another person, which consequently may lead to inaccuracy of the information. Hendriks et al. (2020) discussed the new challenges of the 21st century, focusing on societal diversity. Social workers working among different cultures leads to increased fear and prejudices against the 'unknown' (Hendriks et al., 2020). Cultural knowledge, an essential ability for social professionals, is not a static attribute but a dynamic formation that evolves in parallel with societal changes (Hendriks et al., 2020). The social worker must possess knowledge of the fundamental aspects of his own and foreign cultures while also being cognisant of the individual and communal circumstances prevalent in other cultures (Hendriks et al., 2020). Social professionals must acknowledge the apprehensions and biases towards different cultures and to address them (Hendriks et al., 2020). Hendriks et al. (2020) argue that social workers must recognise that the acceptance of social issues might hinder the socioeconomic status of individuals from diverse origins and the opportunities available to these individuals in society. To further improve diversity within social work, two theoretical frameworks have been developed: an anti-oppressive model and a model of cultural competence (Graham et al., 2009). According to Graham et al. (2009), the anti-oppressive model evolves around all the various constructs that define an individual identity (age, race, gender, nationality, religion, etc.). The second theoretical framework is cultural competence (Graham et al., 2009). The purpose of this model is to make the most of the social workers' cognitive

and sufficient ethical plurality (Graham et al., 2009). Both of these models promote the need to be aware of the diversity. However, this theoretical framework has limitations within its theory, as social worker practitioners maintain discretion in their practice environments. Ultimately, most of the responsibility for change falls on the individual social workers (Graham et al., 2009).

3.4 Professional curiosity & critical thinking

Professional judgement within a social work setting is crucial (Facione et al., 1997). Although professional judgement and critical thinking reflect personal characteristics, as argued by Facione et al. (1997), they are fundamental concepts within the decision-making and problem-solving process. The evaluation process within social settings is about decision-making. It should emphasise that a professional must make unbiased judgements, analyse and interpret information and identify and evaluate the problems in professional settings (Facione et al., 1997). Critical thinking parallels with professional judgement. Defining the fundamentals of 'professional curiosity' occurs more frequently within case reviews and implies that professionals should be more 'curious' about circumstances and challenge what they know (Burton and Revell, 2018). As highlighted by Muirden and Appleton (2022), a lack of professional curiosity and critical analysis is frequently explored in child protection cases. In social work, curiosity is a key skill, which should provide the professional ability to uncover all relevant information, ask thorough questions, and not accept information at face value (Philips et al., 2022). Philips et al. (2022) identify three barriers to professional curiosity. Structural barriers are time constraints (Philips et al., 2022). In simple terms, lacking time on a day-to-day basis consequently leads to an inability to engage in professional settings. Next, relational barriers, referring to good working relationships, and finally emotional barriers. Emotional challenges within professional curiosity lead to a high emotional awareness of being professionally curious (Philips et al., 2022). This supports the argument in the context of social workers' burnouts, case overloads, difficulties in training, and issues with multi-structures of social settings (Thacker et al., 2019). All these barriers lead towards poor decision-making within the initial stages (Alter and Egan, 1997). As social workers experience rising expectations and challenges in fulfilling their roles, comprehending the relationship between these obstacles is critical.

3.5 Assessments of children in special circumstances

Babies rely on others to meet their physical, psychological, emotional, and intellectual necessities (Webb, 2019). In an ideal world, caretaker and infant forms a two-way attachment relationship that serves the infant growing up with experiences of the world and learning to relate to others (Webb, 2019). However, unpredictable situations relating to the living situation, baby's health, family

economics, mental health, substance misuse, and family dynamics produces term so-called "difficult circumstances" (Aptekar and Stocklin, 1997). The term "difficult circumstances" can be a misleading categorisation. Children's vulnerability and victimisation cannot be measured in absolute terms (Aptekar and Stocklin, 1997). However, children to whom this can apply are those children who face difficult circumstances, either from extreme poverty, violence, severe malnutrition or abuse (Aptekar and Stocklin, 1997). Effective intervention and accurate evaluation of complex circumstances are crucial for social workers. Correctly identifying vulnerabilities and prioritising children's needs should occur most of the time; however, this is not always the case. Shifting attention from how to support parents with 'the problem'; social workers' attention shifts through various scenarios in complex circumstances, not always meeting children's needs (Webb, 2019). In research conducted by Brandon et al. (2020), who analysed a total of 368 SCRs between 2014 and 2017, alcohol and drug misuse were classified as parental characteristics in 36% of cases. Consequently, this highlights the importance of understanding and analysing assessment within exceptional circumstances and vulnerabilities in children in substance abuse homes, with a focus on assessment challenges. In the United Kingdom, 2.3 million children are growing up with a vulnerable family background (Children Commissioner for England, 2021).

3.6 Children living in a substance abuse home

Approximately 478,000 children in the United Kingdom live with parents who suffer from substance abuse, either alcohol or drug dependency (Children Commissioner for England, 2019). Approximately 1.6 million children live in families with complex needs for which they have not established support (Children Commissioner for England, 2021). For parents, the impact of drug abuse extends far beyond their usage and impacts the lives of those around them, especially their children (Lewis et al., 2021). Parents' substance use has wide-ranging impacts on the health and well-being of children (Lewis et al., 2021). Children who grow up with parents who suffer from substance abuse are more likely to have psychological issues, poor educational performance, and poor coping strategies (Shearer et al., 2020). Children who are influenced by their parents' drug usage are more likely to have mental and emotional disorders like depression, anxiety, and psychological attachment difficulties (Harwin et al., 2016). Research indicates that evidence of substance misuse is present in two-thirds of childcare applications where social services have expressed concerns (Public Health England, 2021). It's crucial to highlight that true evidence of parents who misuse substances is very hard to establish. The challenge in estimating the extent of the issue lies in the fact that children may react differently when their parents misuse alcohol, making the identification process quite challenging (Department of Health & Social Care, 2023). In fact, the most common predictor of young children not residing with their biological parents is parental substance misuse (Powel et al., 2018). Parents who abuse drugs, for instance, are

more likely to experience high levels of instability, domestic violence, mental illness, and increased risk of homelessness (Lewis et al., 2021). Around 40% of parents start alcohol and drug treatment each year, as much as 80% of alcohol-dependent parents do not receive treatment, with 60% of heroin-dependent parents do not receive treatment (Public Health England, 2021). Alcohol and drug use was evident in 36% of severe instances involving a child who has died or sustained serious injuries (Public Health England, 2021). Consequently, this highlights a significant gap between recognizing the problem, providing support, and addressing the impact on the child's well-being. Despite this significant statistical data, social workers face complex challenges to support and meet children's needs. Detecting parental substance abuse early in a child's life is therefore critical to the prevention and minimising of any associated damage (Baldwin, 2021).

Regrettably, children's services frequently overlook parental substance misuse (Balwin, 2021). According to a study conducted with front-line social workers, highlighting issues related to parental substance misuse (Balwin, 2021). However, it is only acknowledged when it's apparent that it has typically escalated into more serious issues (Galvani and Allnock, 2014). Furthermore, two research studies conducted in the United States support the argument about insufficient recognition of parental substance misuse by social workers. Both studies compared the rates of parental substance misuse with those determined through diagnostic evaluations conducted by researchers on parents (Chaung et al., 2013). In both instances, social workers failed to recognise substance misuse, and as much as 60% of parents satisfied the drug and misuse criteria for harmful or dependent substance use (Chaun et al., 2013). Children who live with parental substance misuse represent those at-risk children, often remaining unnoticed and having their needs disregarded (Cousins and Wells, 2006). They continue to experience abuse and neglect from parents whose judgment is affected by alcohol and drug use (Cousins and Wells, 2006).

Social workers experience several difficulties in identifying parent substance misuse (Baldwin, 2025). Firstly, by concealment, parent hides their substance misuse. Perhaps due to the fear that child protection actions would be taken if social workers became aware of the issue (Baldwin, 2025). In research conducted by Baldwin (2025), who evaluated social workers' experiences who work alongside PSM cases, expressed concern about the fearfulness of disclosing that information, which could lead to potential consequences for the parents. Baldwin (2025) highlights that a lack of knowledge among social workers created further barriers to the correct identification process. Many social workers received training at the introductory level (Baldwin, 2025). Among 400 enquiries examined in the study of PSM, only one-third were detected by social workers (Baldwin, 2025). Comparable investigations into

the identification process were identified in research by Roy (2021), who supports the argument that parents displayed hesitance in revealing substance addiction. The widespread misuse of alcohol among parents in contact with children's social care must be recognised, as alcohol is sold and consumed legally in the UK and its use is less stigmatising than the use of drugs (Baldwin, 2025). Alcohol has been presented as the most harmful of all substances, especially because of its negative effect on others (Nut et al., 2010).

3.7 Serious Cases Relating to Social Work

One of the primary reasons for carrying out SCR is for agencies and individuals to learn lessons to improve their work and promote the welfare of children (Brandon et al., 2009). In the United Kingdom, the formalization of inter-agency child protection procedures, known as Area Review Protection Committees (ARCs), dates back to 1974 (Sidebotham, 2012). Recently, Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) by Local Safeguarding Children Boards replaced them (Sidebotham, 2012). An SCR is mandated in England and Wales whenever a child dies and abuse or neglect is known to be suspected to be a factor in the death (Sidebotham, 2012). One of the primary reasons for carrying out SCR is for agencies and individuals to learn lessons to improve their work collectively to safeguard and promote the welfare of children (Brandon et al., 2009). It is crucial to highlight the importance of multi-structural collaboration in these investigations. Such collaborations include social workers and medical, police, school, and mental health professionals. Each governmental body brings a unique perspective which can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the circumstances surrounding a child's death or serious injury (Brandon et al., 2010). However, despite all the time and resources spent on these reviews, the problems of severe child abuse have not gone away. This prompts a critical question of whether genuinely absorbed the lessons from our experiences and whether any significant changes have been made. Moreover, these studies often reveal weaknesses that have prevented early interventions (Brandon et al., 2009). For instance, these studies often reveal patterns of missed opportunities for detecting signs of abuse or neglect (Brandon et al., 2009). Consequently, the study highlights the necessity for improved training and communication between agencies. In addition, this systematic review can serve the fundamental need for enhanced policy changes. By presenting clear evidence of systematic failures, ultimately serious case reviews must not only seek to analyse failures but also aim to create safer future improved interventions.

3.7.1 Victoria Climbié

Eight-year-old Victoria Climbié died in February 2000 from hypothermia, malnutrition, and physical abuse at the hands of her great-auntie and her cohabitant (Lord Laming, 2003). Victoria Climbié, who endured 128 separate injuries, was described by her pathologist as “the worst case I have ever dealt with, and it's just the worst I have ever heard of.” (Lord Laming, 2003, p. 2). The great-auntie brought Victoria from Ivory Coast to France, then to London, supposedly to improve her education (Reder and Duncan, 2004). During the final 10 months of her life, Victoria had been known to four different social services departments, two police child protection orders, and the specialist care unit of NSPCC and was admitted to the paediatric teams of two other hospitals just 10 days before her death (Lord Laming, 2003). According to Lord Laming’s inquiry report, a lack of good practice between multi-agencies highlighted the necessity for radical changes (Reder and Duncan, 2004). Agencies should have followed straightforward procedures for whom a child was at risk of deliberate harm (Lord Laming, 2003). Failings from Victoria Climbié's case were drawn to multi-structures of child protection services, inadequate training, assessments, and information sharing between agencies (Lord Laming, 2003). The initial analysis and existing procedures lacked, consequently which parallels with effective child practice (Reder and Duncan, 2004). Lord Laming’s 108 recommendations, many of which are referred to as ‘improving the system as a whole’ (Lord Laming, 2003). Lord Laming's recommendations have drawn significant changes within the assessment; the implementation of the Framework for the Assessment of Children in Need and their families, and recommendations evolved by introducing Every Child Matter in Act 2004. Due to recommendations, the National Assessment Framework has undergone extensive improvements to consider multi-structure tools, which will improve responses within social services and other agencies (Cooper, 2005). Also, to some extent in the Victoria Climbié case, social services were focusing more on immediate risk to the child rather than meeting its basic needs (Lord Laming, 2003). It is crucial to emphasise that another challenge in Victoria Climbié's death, as previously noted, was the lack of information sharing. This hindered social workers' ability to understand the full extent of the intervention needed, leading to failures in initial assessments. Victoria Climbié's death provides insights into the challenges of social workers, such as information sharing within the multi-structured system.

3.7.2 Peter Connelly (Baby P)

Peter Connelly, who had extensive media coverage as Baby P, who was only 17 months old, died in the year 2007 (Ray, 2014). Peter Connelly has suffered tremendous injuries to his body, with fractured ribs, missing teeth and marks on his head, and fracture/dislocation of his spine (Haringey Local Safeguarding Children Board, 2009). Baby P and his two siblings were under a child protection plan (Ray, 2014). In

the first executive summary published by Haringey LSCH (2008), the first initial assessment by social workers indicated a need to implement an enquiry of section 47 under the Children Act (1989). Section 47 of the Children Act (1989) requires action to safeguard and promote a child's well-being when there is a suspicion of suffering or likelihood of harm (Legislation, 1989). Although the strategy implemented and the outcome of this assessment were around neglect only, as highlighted by Haringey (2008), the categorisation of physical abuse without reasonable explanation from the parents rather than rough play with children was not followed through by social workers. The Haringey report (2008) highlighted social workers' inability to gather biased evidence and observe parenting and cooperation. Consequently, this underlines an evident gap in the thoroughness of social workers' assessments, as they failed to delve deeper into family dynamics. Understanding family dynamics can provide a crucial deep understanding of a child's environment, potential risks and strengths (Kendal et al., 2010). Establishing a connection with children and parents is essential in the assessment process; unscheduled visits from social workers might improve comprehension of family dynamics and engagement with other siblings (Kendal et al., 2010). Additionally, the Haringey report released in 2009 revealed that all multi-agency structures failed in their information-sharing processes. In addition, all professionals erred in challenging inadequate explanations of the injuries provided by the mother. In an Ofsted report carried out in 2009, following the death of Peter Connolly, Haringey Council was rated as 'inadequate'. Highlighting poor recording practices, a backlog of 400 cases, with initial and core assessments identified as poor quality (Care Quality Commission, 2009). Nevertheless, the death of Peter Connolly's case highlights tragic milestones, reminding social workers of the vital role they play in protecting vulnerable children and emphasising the challenges experienced within the assessment process.

3.7.3 Arthur Lavinjo-Hughes

Arthur Lavinjo-Hughes died in June 2020; he suffered from severe abuse and neglect from his carers, with a total of 130 bruises on Arthur's body at the time of his death (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). Arthur, at the time of his death, had high levels of sodium in his body, an indication of the possibility of salt poisoning (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). Arthur's case was complex, with their mother going to jail and mental health support established for Arthur's case with shifting living accommodations and substantial concerns from grandparents who informed authorities about Arthur's bruising (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). All investigations of bruising by police and social workers lead to no further actions (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). The professional has a limited understanding of Arthur's life and has not fully engaged with him, which has often been silenced by his father (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). Consequently, the assessment failed to gather unbiased information, leading to a

lack of professional curiosity. Furthermore, numerous evaluations neglected to consider objective details regarding the extended Arthurs family members, including the grandparents who expressed apprehensions about his safety (The Child Safeguarding Practise Review Panel, 2022). The professional made certain assumptions about Arthur's father, characterizing him as a caring parent (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). Information sharing in Arthur's case has failed due to errors from the police and social workers. They received photographs showing bruising from the concerned grandmother, but these were filed under different dates (The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2022). As a result, an error occurred in the events, and the implementation of section 47 under the Children Enquiry Act had never been filed.

Chapter 4: Critical Analysis & Conclusion

This chapter explores the decision-making process in social work. Social workers frequently encounter challenging situations that demand critical analysis and appropriate intervention. Initial assessments are vital in social work, particularly when evaluating the risk of harm to children. There has been a lack of emphasis on understanding decision-making and judgment in this context, particularly when analysing Serious Case Reviews. This chapter emphasises that social workers often do not sufficiently reflect on their own decisions, judgments, and biases.

4.1 Critical analysis of decision making

Within all assessment processes, social workers must analyse their decision-making process. Social workers demonstrate a detailed understanding of the complexities in their cases, often achieved through the insightful narratives they engage with (Gregory, 2023). This sense-making process in the initial assessments is crucial, which highlights how decision-making and judgement about the risk of harm to children have received limited attention (Gregory, 2023). How social workers interpret information to reach decisions and how they make decisions often results in challenges within that process (Gregory, 2023). According to a study conducted by Gregory (2023), who explores the decision-making process within the assessment in social work settings, the concept by ethnographic approaches. Emerging themes in the assessment process, such as initial formulations, refer to formulating cases to identify key factors within the assessment process (Gregory, 2023). For example, assumptions about parents' characteristics often remain unexamined, leading to failings in the assessment processes (Gregory, 2023). Gregory (2023) highlighted the development of the narrative by social workers, who often assess the information given to them, feelings and relationships and create their hypothesis and their narratives. Finally, the adopted account refers to the function of decision-making processes (Gregory, 2023). All sense-making (Gregory, 2023), professional curiosity (Muirden and Appleton, 2022), critical thinking as well as burnouts (Burns and MacCarthy, 2012) experiences by social workers closely correlate with each other, all physical and emotional states of the individuals, leads to poor decision making and judgment in the evaluation processes (Marc and Osvat, 2013; Michailidis and Banks, 2016). However, it is crucial to highlight that not all challenges experienced by social workers can be referred to as an emotional state and decision-making. Often, challenges lie within the structural settings of social work. It's hard to determine the correlation between all physical attributes and

outcomes of the cases, purely drawing it to initial assessments, as all assessments within social settings play crucial roles in understanding the complexities of the cases.

4.2 "The Invisible Child"

This chapter draws attention to a key theme recurring through Serious Case Studies. It draws attention to the failure to engage with children in the assessment process, which leads to child voices and needs not meet. It draws attention to the critical attention required to develop relationships with adults.

One overwhelming theme that persists in cases of SCRs is the enduring problem of a child's voice being lost and not heard. The theme of children not being heard or seen is a feature of most studies of SCR. The 'invisible' child to professionals creates barriers within the assessment and analysing process. While social workers analyse and assess children's well-being and family dynamics, young people are often insufficiently consulted or engaged in the process. Brandon et al. (2009), research supports the argument that invisible children are not seen or not being heard due to being kept out of sight, or they are unable to speak due to fear or trauma. A social worker's objective analysis revolves around gathering unbiased information about families, with the identification of vulnerabilities. Often social workers avoid being 'judgemental' and are overwhelmed with complex family circumstances, for example, substance misuse (Brandon et al., 2009). Ofsted's (2011) report evaluated children's perspectives, which social workers overlooked in their assessment process. This highlights the recognition of errors from social workers. Similarly, Ferguson (2017) argues that children become invisible in the assessment framework due to breakdowns in communication between professionals and agencies. Ferguson (2017) argues that the effect of these systematic reviews and analyses and extensive levels of casework leads to a lack of time to develop the depth of relationship necessary to keep children safe. Furthermore, when analysing SCRs in instances where children have died, professionals were in the presence of abused children (Ferguson, 2017). Consequently, workers did not get close enough to them to discover abuse. Brandon et al. (2008) identified the start-again syndrome when social workers inadequately consider the parental history and risk factors in cases. Start-again syndrome implies a tendency of practitioners to perceive new circumstances, like childbirth, while neglecting the historical context and risk patterns associated with the family (Brandon et al., 2008). Consequently, workers did not get close enough to them to discover abuse. Brandon et al. (2008) identified the start-again syndrome when social workers inadequately consider the parental history and risk factors in cases. The children 'invisibility' refers to lacking engagement with them despite their physical presence.

The objective of effective practice should be expressed in a manner that incorporates all senses and promotes familiarity. The goal of good practice must be stated in a language that includes all senses and closeness. Research indicates that in the absence of meaningful engagement—such as direct eye contact, discussion, engaged listening, play, touch, and close observation—crucial aspects of a child's experience may remain unrecognised (Ferguson, 2017). The phrase "unheld child" is more fitting for this occurrence since it emphasises the lack of physical and emotional connection required to enter and join the child's world. In the case of Arthur Lavinjo-Hughes social workers engage in 90-minute home visits, in which they observe and talk to the children. Consequently, this leads to unnoticed intervention and the inability to observe the necessary intervention to prevent the outcome.

For example, in the research carried out by Ferguson (2017), who carried out participant observation with a total of twenty-four social workers. Ferguson (2017) highlighted that in almost a third of the cases, social workers regarded children as lacking the verbal capacity and understanding to be seen on their own. Understanding children of all ages goes beyond verbal and nonverbal communication, and a social worker's ability to understand child needs highlights how social workers gather information. Ferguson (2017), who shadowed social workers in the field during home visits, noted that social workers engaged in conversations for five to fifteen minutes with the children, with the shortest interaction lasting just two minutes. Insufficient time spent with the children underscores essential dynamics in social work practices, resulting in children becoming overlooked in these practices.

4.3 Challenges in inter-agency communication

A recurring theme through serious case studies refers back to information sharing between agencies. In all cases, a noticeable lack of communication created further barriers in correctly identifying potential children at risk. Moreover, in recent studies carried out by Dickens et al. (2022), who carried out a comparison of SCRs from 2003 to 2019, it has been highlighted that poor record-keeping, information sharing and poor cooperation between agencies were recurring themes. Furthermore, persistent issues about information-sharing arise from fears and misconceptions about violating confidentiality, which may indicate broader societal and cultural concerns (Dickens et al., 2022). The fear of breaching data protection law was noted in SCR between 2011 and 14. Similarly, further analysis of SCRs carried out by Chapman (2015) highlights that information sharing between agencies on a basis is dismissed, often lacking follow-ups, resulting in many cases of high risk missed. Many recommendations, as pointed out by Chapman (2025), effective inter-agency could perhaps result in further improvements of social workers assessments.

4.4 Conclusion

Understanding the challenges experienced by social workers is multi-layered. The challenges experienced by social workers of emotional barriers, organisational structures, and critical thinking parallel in the context of decision-making. Any barriers experienced by social workers carry consequences in the decision-making process, which impacts the evaluation and outcome for in-need children. Poor decision-making can lead to inadequate support and harmful outcomes, highlighting the importance of addressing these issues within the social work profession. Social workers who do not engage within the family setting and lack engagement with the family dynamic, often leading to the invisibility of the child, are problematic. It's crucial to emphasise that children's voices are frequently lost and not heard enough. Moreover, social workers challenging their biases and judgement could improve outcomes for correctly identifying vulnerable children. Organisational structures highlight problematic struggles within the assessment of the most vulnerable. Poor information sharing between agencies and a lack of successful responses from social workers create further implementation. Improved awareness of these issues and improved training within these challenges can perhaps enhance and emphasise the challenges experienced by social workers. Analysis of Serious Case Reviews provides learning lessons for improved assessment and intervention from social workers, which are vital in prevention. Furthermore, future research would look into decision-making within specific contexts and undertake more in-depth analyses of stepchildren. This analysis of stepchildren is valuable because it may reveal more complex challenges in effectively identifying children in need and the care they require.

References

Abuaddous, M., Bataineh, H. and Alabood, E. (2018) Burnout and auditor's judgment decision making: An experimental investigation into control risk assessment. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 22(4), pp.1-16.

Alston, M. (2020) *Research for social workers: An introduction to methods*. Routledge

Alter, C. and Egan, M. (1997) 'Logic modeling: A tool for teaching critical thinking in social work practice'. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 33(1), pp.85-102, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10437797.1997.10778855> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Aptekar, L. and Stocklin, D. (1997.) 'Children in particularly difficult circumstances' *Handbook of cross-cultural psychology*, 2, pp.377-412.

Asquith, S., Clark, C.L. and Waterhouse, L. (2005). *The role of the social worker in the 21st century: A literature review* (Vol. 25). Edinburgh: Scottish Executive Education Department.

Baginsky, M., 2023. Parents' views on improving relationships with their social workers. *Journal of Social Work*, 23(1), pp.3-18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/14680173221101244> (Accessed on 19/02/2025).

Bailhache, M., Leroy, V., Pillet, P. and Salmi, L.R. (2013) 'Is early detection of abused children possible?: a systematic review of the diagnostic accuracy of the identification of abused children'. *BMC pediatrics*, 13, pp.1-1, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2431-13-202> (Accessed on 07/02/2025).

Baldwin, H. (2021) 'Responses to Parental Substance Misuse by Children's Social Care Services in England', Available at: https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/29117/1/Baldwin_201057873_CorrectedThesisClean.pdf (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Baldwin, H. (2025) 'Identification of parental substance misuse by children's social care departments in England'. *Children and Youth Services Review*, p.108123. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2025.108123> (Accessed on 16/02/2025).

Biehal, N. (2014) Maltreatment in foster care: A review of the evidence. *Child abuse review*, 23(1), pp.48-60.

Bowles, W. and Alston, M. (2013) *Research for social workers: An introduction to methods*. Routledge.

Brandon, M., Bailey, S., Belderson, P., Gardner, R., Sidebotham, P., Dodsworth, J., Warren, C., Black, J. and Norfolk, N.H.S. (2009) 'Understanding serious case reviews and their impact'. London, Department for Children, Schools and Families.

Brandon, M., Bailey, S.E. and Belderson, P. (2010) 'Building on the learning from serious case reviews: a two-year analysis of child protection database notifications 2007-2009', London: Department for Education.

Brandon, M., Belderson, P., Sorensen, P., Dickens, J., Sidebotham, P., Cleaver, H., Garstang, J., Harris, J. and Wate, R. (2020) 'Complexity and challenge: A triennial analysis of SCRs 2014-2017', Available at: https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/id/eprint/74649/1/TRIENNIAL_SCR_REPORT_2014_to_2017.pdf (Accessed on 28/03/2025).

Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Methods*. 5th ed.Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Burns, K. and MacCarthy, J. (2012) An impossible task? Implementing the recommendations of child abuse inquiry reports in a context of high workloads in child protection and welfare, Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/10468/732> (Accessed on 02/02/2025).

Burton, V. and Revell, L. (2018) 'Professional curiosity in child protection: Thinking the unthinkable in a neo-liberal world'. *The British journal of social work*, 48(6), pp.1508-1523. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/bjsw/article/48/6/1508/4604651> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Care Quality Commission. (2009) 'Inspection of progress made in the provision of safeguarding services in the London Borough of Haringey', Available at: <https://files.ofsted.gov.uk/v1/file/50002217> (Accessed on 12/02/2025).

Cheng, H.G. and Phillips, M.R. (2014) 'Secondary analysis of existing data: opportunities and implementation'. *Shanghai archives of psychiatry*, 26(6), p.371.

Children Act (1989), Available at:

https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/41/pdfs/ukpga_19890041_en.pdf (Accessed on 30/01/2025).

Children Commissioner for England (2019) 'estimating the prevalence of the toxic trio' of family issues for each local area in England', Available at:

<https://assets.childrenscommissioner.gov.uk/wpuploads/2019/07/cco-vulnerability-2019-tech-report-2.pdf> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Chuang, E., Wells, R., Bellettiere, J. and Cross, T.P. (2013) 'Identifying the substance abuse treatment needs of caregivers involved with child welfare'. *Journal of substance abuse treatment*, 45(1), pp.118-125. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsat.2013.01.007> (Accessed on 15.02.2025).

Clark, G. (2013) Secondary data. *Methods in Human Geography*, pp.57-73.

Cooper, A. (2005) 'Surface and depth in the Victoria Climbié inquiry report'. *Child & Family Social Work*, 10(1), pp.1-9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2206.2005.00350.x> (Accessed on 09/02/2025).

Cousins, W. and Wells, K. (2005). "One more for my baby": foetal alcohol syndrome and its implications for social workers'. *Child Care in Practice*, 11(3), pp.375-383. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13575270500151953> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Cree, V. and Myers, S. (2008) *Social work: Making a difference*. Policy Press.

Dalley, G. (1991) Beliefs and behaviour: professionals and the policy process. *Journal of Aging Studies*, 5(2), pp.163-180. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-4065\(91\)90004-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-4065(91)90004-C) (Accessed on 04/02/2025).

Department for Education (2024) 'Children in Need', Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/children-in-need> (Accessed on 07/03/2025).

Department of Health & Social Care (2023) 'Evaluation of the Children of alcohol dependent parents programme innovation fund :full report' , Available at:
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/evaluation-of-the-children-of-alcohol-dependent-parents-programme-innovation-fund/evaluation-of-the-children-of-alcohol-dependent-parents-programme-innovation-fund-full-report#:~:text=Meanwhile%2C%20a%20considerable%20number%20of,parent%20in%202019%20to%202020.> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Dickens, J., Taylor, J., Cook, L., Cossar, J., Garstang, J., Rimmer, J. (2022) 'Serious case reviews 1998 to 2019: continuities, changes and challenges', Available at:
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/639702918fa8f55307a28c61/Serious_case_reviews_1998_to_2019_-_continuities__changes_and_challenges.pdf (Accessed on 16/03/2025).

Dominelli, L. (2002) Values in social work: Contested entities with enduring qualities. *Critical practice in social work*, pp.15-27.

Facione, P.A., Facione, N.C. and Giancarlo, C.A. (1997) 'Professional judgment and the disposition toward critical thinking'. Retrieved Nov, 21, p.2020. Available at:
https://t.insightassessment.com/var/ezflow_site/storage/pdf/Prof_Jdgmnt_&_Dsp_CT_97_Frnch1999.pdf (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Fish, S. and Hardy, M. (2015) Complex issues, complex solutions: Applying complexity theory in social work practice. *Nordic Social Work Research*, 5(sup1), pp.98-114.

Ferguson, H. (2017) 'How children become invisible in child protection work: Findings from research into day-to-day social work practice'. *British Journal of Social Work*, 47(4), pp.1007-1023.

Galvani, S. and Allnock, D. (2014) 'The nature and extent of substance use education in qualifying social work programmes in England'. *Social Work Education*, 33(5), pp.573-588. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2014.919067> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Graham, J.R., Bradshaw, C. and Trew, J.L. (2009) Addressing cultural barriers with Muslim clients: An agency perspective. *Administration in Social Work*, 33(4), pp.387-406

Gregory, M. (2023) 'Story-building and narrative in social workers' case-talk: A model of social work sensemaking'. *Child & Family Social Work*, 28(4), pp.949-959, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.13014> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Hanley, J. (2024) 'The Social Work Public Perception Myth' *The British Journal of Social Work*, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcae145> (Accessed on 02/02/2025).

Haringey Local Safeguarding Children Board. (2008) 'Serious case review, 'Child A', First serious case review, *Department for Education*, Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7a468a40f0b66eab99b045/first_serious_case_review_overview_report_relating_to_peter_connelly_dated_november_2008.pdf (Accessed on 12/02/2025).

Haringey Local Safeguarding Children Board. (2009) 'Serious case review, 'Child A', Second serious case review, *Department for Education*, Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a8155a4e5274a2e8ab536d2/second_serious_case_overview_report_relating_to_peter_connelly_dated_march_2009.pdf (Accessed on 12/02/2025).

Health and Safety at work (2024) "Summary Statistics for Great Britain 2024", Available at: <https://www.hse.gov.uk/statistics/assets/docs/hssh2324.pdf> (Accessed on 04/02/2025).

Heaton, J. (1998) Secondary analysis of qualitative data. *Social Research Methods*, 506.

Hendriks, P., Kloppenburg, R., Boccagni, P., Claes, E., Csoba, J., Ciriano, E.J.G., Kinos, S., McLaughlin, H. and Schrooten, M. (2020) 'Social work and challenges of urban diversity', Available at: <https://www.archive2.eassw.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Urban-diversities-booklet-final-version-january-23-2020.pdf> (Accessed on 06/02/2025).

Hepworth, D.H., Rooney, R.H., Rooney.D.G., Strom-Gottfried, K (2002) *Direct Social Work Practise: Theory and Practise*, 10th edition.

His Majesty's Government (2006) 'Working Together to Safeguard Children', Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/4155839.pdf> (Accessed on 02/02/2025).

Hope, J. and Van Wyk, C. (2018) 'Intervention strategies used by social workers in emergency child protection'. *Social work*, 54(4), pp.421-437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15270/54-4-670> (Accessed on 07/03/2025).

Jacklin, A., Robinson, C. and Torrance, H. (2006) When lack of data is data: do we really know who our looked-after children are?, *European journal of special needs education*, 21(1), pp.1-20, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856250500491773> (Accessed on 04/02/2025).

Johnston, M.P. (2014) Secondary data analysis: A method of which the time has come. *Qualitative and quantitative methods in libraries*, 3(3), pp.619-626.

Jones, R. (2019) '1970-2020: A fifty year history the personal social services and social work in England and across the United Kingdom'. *Social Work and Social Sciences Review*, 21(3), pp.8-44.

Kendal, S., Rodger, J., Palmer, H. (2010) 'The use of whole family assessment to identify the needs of families with multiple problems', *Department for Education*, Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7a4ea0ed915d1fb3cd6f04/DFE-RR045.pdf> (Accessed on 12/02/2025).

Laming, H.B. (2009) *The protection of children in England: A progress report* (Vol. 330). The Stationery Office.

Laming, Lord (2003) 'The Victoria Climbié Inquiry', Available at: <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7c5edeed915d696ccfc51b/5730.pdf> (Accessed on 08/02/2025).

Lamponen, T. and Aarnio, N. (2024) Social workers' assessment of a child's need for services as 'craftwork' practice. *Journal of Social Work Practice*, 38(2), pp.129-142, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650533.2024.2302603> (Accessed on 02/02/2025).

Lewis, Q.J., Smith, B.D., Offiong, A., Prioleau, M. and Powell, T.W. (2021) 'When a house is never a home: Housing instability among youth affected by parental drug abuse'. *Child abuse & neglect*, 118, p.105131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2021.105131> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Lock (2013) 'Serious case review re Daniel Pelka: born 15th of July 2007 died 3rd March 2012', Available at: <https://pdscp.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/SCR-Daniel-Pelka-2013.pdf> (Accessed on 05/02/2025).

London Metropolitan University, (2022). *Academic integrity*. Available at: <https://student.londonmet.ac.uk/your-studies/mphil--phd-professional-doctorates/research-ethics/> (Accessed on 23/02/2025)

Macdonald, G., Lewis, J., Macdonald, K., Gardner, E., Murphy, L., Adams, C., Ghate, D., Cotmore, R. and Green, J. (2014) 'THE SAAF STUDY: evaluation of the Safeguarding Children Assessment and Analysis Framework (SAAF), compared with management as usual, for improving outcomes for children and young people who have experienced, or are at risk of, maltreatment: study protocol for a randomised controlled trial'. *Trials*, 15, pp.1-12. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1186/1745-6215-15-453.pdf>

Marc, C. and Osvat, C. (2013) Stress and burnout among social workers. *Revista de Asistentă Socială*, (3), p.121.

McFadden, P. (2015) 'Measuring burnout among UK social workers: A Community Care study'. *Community Care*. Available at: <https://www.qub.ac.uk/sites/media/Media,514081,en.pdf> (Accessed on 05/02/2025).

Mehrotra, G.R., Hudson, K.D. and Self, J.M. (2019) A critical examination of key assumptions underlying diversity and social justice courses in social work. *Journal of Progressive Human Services*, 30(2), pp.127-147. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10428232.2018.1507590> (Accessed on 04/02/2025).

Michailidis, E. and Banks, A.P. (2016) The relationship between burnout and risk-taking in workplace decision-making and decision-making style. *Work & Stress*, 30(3), pp.278-292.

Milner, J., Myers, S. and O'Byrne, P. (2020) *Assessment in social work*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Moriarty, J., Baginsky, M. and Manthorpe, J. (2015) 'Literature review of roles and issues within the social work profession in England', Available at:

https://kclpure.kcl.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/52887695/literature_review_roles_and_issues_within_the_social_work_profession_in_england_2015.pdf (Accessed on 31/01/2025).

Munro, E. (1999) Common errors of reasoning in child protection work. *Child abuse & neglect*, 23(8), pp.745-75

National Health Service (2023) 'Dissociative disorders', Available at: <https://www.nhs.uk/mental-health/conditions/dissociative-disorders/#:~:text=dissociative%20identity%20disorder-,Depersonalisation%2Dderealisation%20disorder,feel%20the%20world%20is%20unreal>. (Accessed on 23/02/2025).

Naveed, S. and Rana, N.S. (2013) Job burnout process and its implications in HRM practices: A case study of trainee doctors in public health organization. *Asian Journal of Business Management*, 5(1), pp.113-123.

NSPCC (2014) ' Culture and faith: learning from case reviews", Available at: https://learning.nspcc.org.uk/media/1332/learning-from-case-reviews_culture-and-faith.pdf (Accessed on 07/02/2025).

NSPCC. (2024) 'Statistics briefing: child deaths due to abuse or neglect', Available at: <https://learning.nspcc.org.uk/media/ryodwhyg/child-deaths-abuse-neglect.pdf> (Accessed on 06/02/2025).

Nutt, D.J., King, L.A. and Phillips, L.D. (2010) 'Drug harms in the UK: a multicriteria decision analysis', *The Lancet*, 376(9752), pp.1558-1565. Available at: <https://www.ias.org.uk/uploads/pdf/News%20stories/dnutt-lancet-011110.pdf> (Accessed on 16/02/2025).

Oaks, D.H. (2012) 'Protect the children'. *Ensign*, 11, pp.43-4, Available at: <http://www.davidson-law.net/CR/2012%20Oct%200207%20OaksDH%2012.pdf> (Accessed on 07/02/2025).

Okitikpi, T. ed. (2011) *Social control and the use of power in social work with children and families*. Dorset: Russell House Publishing.

Osmo, R. and Benbenishty, R. (2004) Children at risk: Rationales for risk assessments and interventions. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 26(12), pp.1155-1173. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2004.05.006> (Accessed on 31/01/2025).

Pearlman, W. (2023) 'Emotional sensibility: Exploring the methodological and ethical implications of research participants' emotions'. *American Political Science Review*, 117(4), pp.1241-1254. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055422001253> (Accessed on 20/03/2025).

Phillips, J., Ainslie, S., Fowler, A. and Westaby, C. (2022) 'What does professional curiosity mean to you?': an exploration of professional curiosity in probation. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 52(1), pp.554-572, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcab019> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Phillips, J., Westaby, C., Fowler, A. and Ainslie, S. (2022) 'Putting professional curiosity into practice', Available at: <https://www.justiceinspectors.gov.uk/hmiprobation/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/2022/08/Academic-Insights-Phillips-et-al-v1.5.pdf> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Pinkney, L., Penhale, B., Manthorpe, J., Perkins, N., Reid, D. and Hussein, S. (2008) 'Voices from the frontline: social work practitioners' perceptions of multi-agency working in adult protection in England and Wales' *The Journal of Adult Protection*, 10(4), pp.12-24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/14668203200800022> (Accessed on 04/02/2025).

Powell, M.A., McArthur, M., Chalmers, J., Graham, A., Moore, T., Spriggs, M. and Taplin, S. (2018) 'Sensitive topics in social research involving children'. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 21(6), pp.647-660. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2018.1462882> (Accessed on 07/02/2025).

Power, L. and Dean, L. (2023) Expectations versus reality: achieving impact from social work practitioner research in challenging circumstances. *The British Journal of Social Work*, 53(7), pp.3436-3455, Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcad174> (Accessed on 06/02/2025).

Public Health England (2021) 'Parents with alcohol and drug problems: adult treatment and children and family services', Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/parents-with-alcohol-and-drug-problems-support-resources/parents-with-alcohol-and-drug-problems-guidance-for-adult-treatment-and-children-and-family-services> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Ravalier, J., Wainwright, E., Clabburn, O., Loon, M. and Smyth, N. (2021) Working conditions and wellbeing in UK social workers. *Journal of Social Work*, 21(5), pp.1105-1123.

Reamer, F. (2018) *Social work values and ethics*. Columbia University Press.

Reder, P. and Duncan, S. (2004) 'Making the most of the Victoria Climbié inquiry report'. *Child Abuse Review: Journal of the British Association for the Study and Prevention of Child Abuse and Neglect*, 13(2), pp.95-114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/car.834> (Accessed on 08/02/2025).

Roy, J. (2021) 'Children living with parental substance misuse: A cross-sectional profile of children and families referred to children's social care'. *Child & Family Social Work*, 26(1), pp.122-131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12795> (Accessed on 16/02/2025).

Shearer, R.D., Howell, B.A., Bart, G. and Winkelman, T.N. (2020) 'Substance use patterns and health profiles among US adults who use opioids, methamphetamine, or both, 2015-2018'. *Drug and alcohol dependence*, 214, p.108162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2020.108162> (Accessed on 15/02/2025).

Sidebotham, P. (2012) What do serious case reviews achieve?. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, 97(3), pp.189-192.

Sidebotham, P., Brandon, M., Bailey, S., Belderson, P., Garstang, J., Harrison, E., Retzer, A. and Sorensen, P. (2016) 'Pathways to harm, pathways to protection: a triennial analysis of serious case reviews 2011-2014' *Department for Education*.

Simeon, D. (2004) 'Depersonalisation disorder: a contemporary overview'. *CNS drugs*, 18, pp.343-354. Available at: <http://depersonalizace.info/file/2004.pdf> (Accessed on 05/02/2025).

Skivenes, M. and Stenberg, H. (2015) 'Risk assessment and domestic violence—how do child welfare workers in three countries assess and substantiate the risk level of a 5-year-old girl?'. *Child & Family Social Work*, 20(4), pp.424-436. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12092>

Social Work England (2020) 'Professional standards guidance', Available at: <https://www.socialworkengland.org.uk/media/3453/professional-standards-guidance.pdf> (Accessed on 07/03/2025).

Social work for England (2017) 'Social work in England: First Reflection' Available at:
https://www.socialworkengland.org.uk/media/3742/social-work-in-england_first-reflections.pdf
(Accessed on 30/01/2025).

Thacker, H., Anka, A. and Penhale, B. (2019) 'Could curiosity save lives? An exploration into the value of employing professional curiosity and partnership work in safeguarding adults under the Care Act 2014'. *The Journal of Adult Protection*, 21(5), pp.252-267. Available at:
<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/jap-04-2019-0014/full/pdf> (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

The Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel (2022) 'National review into murders of Arthur Labinjo-Hughed and Star Hobson', Available at:
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/628e262d8fa8f556203eb4f8/ALH_SH_National_Review_26-5-22.pdf (Accessed on 14/02/2025).

Thompson, N. (2024) *Understanding social work: Preparing for practice*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Titterton, M. (2004) *Risk and risk taking in health and social welfare*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

Turley, R., Roberts, S., Foster, C., Warner, N., El-Banna, A., Evans, R., Nurmatov, U., Walpita, Y. and Scourfield, J. (2022) 'Staff wellbeing and retention in children's social work: Systematic review of interventions'. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 32(3), pp.281-309. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/10497315211052639> (Accessed on 08/02/2025).

Webb, N.B. (2019) *Social work practice with children*. Guilford Publications.

Wickham, R.J. (2019) 'Secondary analysis research'. *Journal of the advanced practitioner in oncology*, 10(4), p.395.

Wood, A. (2016) 'Wood report: Review of the role and functions of Local Safeguarding Children Boards', Available at:
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a80676fe5274a2e8ab4ff28/Alan_Wood_review.pdf
(Accessed on 16/03/2025).

World Health Organisation (2024) 'Child maltreatment', Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/child-maltreatment> (Accessed on 07/02/2025).